

Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Role

Training and Implementation (2023–2024)

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ES Data Collector Role

Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Data Collectors contributed to the study of how solar eclipses affect life on Earth by recording environmental soundscapes using small, open-source devices named AudioMoths. During the October 14, 2023 annular solar eclipse and the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse, volunteer scientists across the United States deployed AudioMoths outdoors for five consecutive days: two days before the eclipse, the day of the eclipse, and two days after.

This multi-day deployment window enabled comparisons between baseline non-eclipse-day soundscapes and eclipse-day conditions, allowing scientists to identify changes in environmental sound and animal activity associated with the rapid shifts in light and temperature that occur during solar eclipses. Each recording became part of the larger Eclipse Soundscapes dataset, archived publicly in the Eclipse Soundscapes Community on Zenodo. Resulting analyses have been published in a peer-reviewed article in *Ecology & Evolution*.

This manual compiles the guidance provided to ES Data Collectors through the Eclipse Soundscapes website, live and recorded webinars, and structured email communications. It also documents key participation structures, accessibility considerations, and implementation decisions that shaped the Data Collector role during the 2023 and 2024 eclipse cycles. The content reflects materials made publicly available to participants and is preserved here for transparency, documentation, and long-term reuse.

Role Summary

Purpose

Collect soundscapes audio recordings during eclipse week.

Core Responsibilities

- Register AudioMoth device (ES ID)
- Set-up and Deploy AudioMoth correctly
- Record latitude/longitude
- Submit metadata via handwritten notes and an online form
- Mail microSD card

Outcome

Site-level raw audio archived publicly on Zenodo.

Analysis conducted by Soundscapes Subject Matter Experts.

Data Collector Learning Objectives

The ES Data Collector role was designed as a hands-on scientific learning experience. Through participation, individuals had the opportunity to:

- Prepare an acoustic recording device for scientific data collection
- Deploy an acoustic recording device in a real-world outdoor environment.
- Collect and submit accurate geospatial metadata, including latitude, longitude, and deployment timing.
- Interpret eclipse timing data (eclipse maximum and percentage of Sun coverage) in relation to their recording location.
- Contribute original environmental audio data to a publicly archived scientific dataset.
- Engage in a structured workflow connecting device registration, metadata submission, and physical data return.

Participation in the Data Collector role provided experiential engagement with field-based data collection, geospatial reasoning, time-series analysis concepts, and open science infrastructure.

These opportunities align with broader NASA Science Activation goals to increase public use of NASA data assets (e.g., eclipse timing and coverage datasets) and to deepen understanding of the processes of science through authentic participation in data collection and stewardship.

Participation Requirements & Operational Procedures

The Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) program invited volunteers to become Data Collectors during the October 14, 2023, annular solar eclipse and the April 8, 2024, total solar eclipse. This section outlines the essential requirements and steps involved for participants.

Before Deployment

- Sign-up as an ES Data Collector through the Eclipse Soundscapes website in order to receive important and time relevant role and project information and updates via email
- Complete the Apprentice Training, which introduces important eclipse information, project science goals, and eclipse safety information.
 - Severino, M., & Kline, T. (2025, November 24). ES Apprentice Role Curriculum: Solar Eclipses and Multi-Sensory Observing (Informal Education). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17703003>
- Attend or watch a recorded [Training Webinar](#) and review all [ES Data Collector Training](#) modules
- Assemble or receive a [Data Collector Kit](#).

AudioMoth Preparation

Preparation steps varied depending on how the AudioMoth was obtained:

- If provided by ES in 2024: verify that the device clock was correctly set
- If provided by ES in 2023: install fresh batteries, insert a new SD card, and set the device clock
- If using a personally owned AudioMoth: flash the device with required firmware, install the SD card and batteries, set the clock, and register for a unique ES ID number

More detailed information for all of the above preparation steps can be found in [Asynchronous Training & Instructions](#).

Deployment and Recording

- Deploy the AudioMoth for a five-day recording window, consisting of:
 - two days before the eclipse date
 - the day of the eclipse
 - two days after the eclipse
- Transport the Data Collector Kit to the recording location at the start of the deployment window
- Start recording by setting the AudioMoth switch to “Default” and noting the recording start time
- Secure the AudioMoth inside the waterproof bag to an immovable outdoor object (such as a tree or pole) using zip ties, with:
 - the flat green circuit board facing outward
 - the batteries positioned against the object
- Record location notes, including:
 - latitude and longitude in Decimal Degrees
 - brief observations about the surrounding environment
- Leave the AudioMoth in place for the full deployment period

More detailed information for all of the above preparation steps can be found in [Asynchronous Training & Instructions](#).

Eclipse Day (Optional)

- On eclipse day, Data Collectors were invited but not required to also participate as ES Observers and make qualitative observations using their senses
 - Severino, M., & Bauer, D. J. (2026). Eclipse Soundscapes Observer Role Training and Resources Manual (2023–2024). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18633602>

Device Retrieval and Submission

- Retrieve the AudioMoth at the end of the deployment period
- Stop recording by setting the switch to “USB/Off” and noting the stop time
- Submit Field Notes via an online form on the ES website as soon as possible after retrieval, no later than 2 weeks after the eclipse.
- Remove the SD card from the AudioMoth
- Return the SD card and written field notes information to the ES team using the provided padded envelope or mail to the address listed on the ES website

More detailed information for all of the above preparation steps can be found in [Asynchronous Training & Instructions](#), which documents the training information that participants received. Participation in a single eclipse event met the requirements for the Data Collector role; volunteers were not required to participate in both eclipses.

Data Collection Kit Components

Each Data Collector assembled or received a kit that included:

- 1 AudioMoth Device
- 1 waterproof plastic bag (small/1 pint or medium/1 quart size freezer bag will work),
- 2-3 zip ties (to attach AudioMoth to tree/pole),
- 1 padded return envelope (to mail ES Team your MicroSD card),
- 3 AA batteries
- one 64GB Extreme UHS Speed Class 3 (U3) microSDXC card (not included if you purchase an AudioMoth). Please note that the ES Team will not be able to return MicroSD cards to participants who send us their data.

Free ES Data Collector Kit

To reduce financial barriers and expand participation, the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) team provided a limited number of free ES Data Collector kits for both the 2023 annular and 2024 total solar eclipses. ES provided 545 free Data Collector kits across both eclipses (155 in 2023 and 390 in 2024). Kits were distributed through partner networks, including NASA@My Library, and directly to individuals via an online application process. Because demand exceeded available kits, individual applications were reviewed and, after separated by eclipse proximity and state, selected through a lottery process. Additional participants constructed their own AudioMoth-based recording kits following publicly available instructions.

Free kit applications were submitted through structured online Google forms:

- 2023 Annular Eclipse ES Data Collector Free Kit Application ([Appendix 1](#))
- 2024 Total Solar Eclipse ES Data Collector Free Kit Application ([Appendix 2](#))

Forms collected applicant contact information, mailing address, intended data collection zip code, and agreement to complete required training, deploy equipment according to protocol, and return the microSD card containing recorded soundscape data.

Eligibility and Prioritization

Participants were required to be 13 years of age or older to serve as an ES Data Collector. However, only individuals 18 years of age or older were eligible to apply directly for a free kit as mailing addresses were required. Youth participants could participate under adult supervision, and a guardian or supervising adult was required to complete the application on their behalf.

Because kit quantities were limited, priority was given to applicants located in areas expected to experience 70% or greater eclipse coverage, helping ensure scientifically meaningful data collection during significant light-change conditions. Geographic distribution was also considered during selection.

Accessibility, Equity, and Trust-Based Design

Providing free kits was an intentional equity strategy to ensure that access to recording equipment did not limit participation in NASA-supported research. Application forms were designed to be screen reader-compatible and clearly structured, aligning with the project's Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework.

In addition to individual applicants, ES partnered with organizations such as **NASA@My Library** to distribute kits through trusted community institutions, further broadening public access.

The kit distribution model reflects a trust-based participatory science design. Volunteers committed in good faith to complete training, deploy equipment as instructed, and return data. By lowering financial barriers while maintaining clear participation expectations, ES connected community access with rigorous scientific contribution.

AudioMoth Device Information

The AudioMoth is a compact, low-cost, open-source acoustic recorder developed by Open Acoustic Devices. It is a full-spectrum recording device capable of capturing sounds at both audible and ultrasonic frequencies. AudioMoth records uncompressed audio directly to a microSD card at sampling rates ranging from 8,000 to 384,000 samples per second. The device can also function as a full-spectrum USB microphone.

Additional technical specifications are available from Open Acoustic Devices:

<https://www.openacousticdevices.info/audiomoth>

Providing participants with enough baseline technical information to understand how the equipment worked, without overloading them with excessive technical details, helped welcome both novice and tech-savvy participants. In addition to general device information, ES Data Collectors were provided with concise, role-relevant “quick facts” that directly supported required setup and deployment procedures.

Participant-Facing Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

AudioMoth Quick Facts

- The AudioMoth has a switch with three modes: **Custom, USB/Off, Default**.
- The device is **not recording** when the switch is set to “USB/Off.”
- ES Data Collectors move the switch to “**Default**” to begin recording.
- The AudioMoth does **not** automatically log latitude and longitude. Data Collectors are responsible for finding and submitting this information to the ES team.
- If the batteries are removed, the internal clock must be reset. (Clock resetting steps provided in training materials.)
- Some AudioMoth setup is required **before deployment day**. See the “Prepare Equipment” training section.
- If purchasing an AudioMoth independently, note that the device does **not** come with a microSD card.
- The AudioMoth requires an **Extreme UHS Speed Class 3 (U3) microSDXC card**. The U3 classification ensures that the card’s write speed is fast enough to keep up with high-sample-rate audio recording.
- Memory card guidance is available from Open Acoustic Devices:
<https://www.openacousticdevices.info/sd-card-guide>

Kit Accessibility and Universal Design

Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) integrated accessibility and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles into the design of the Data Collector kits from the beginning. In addition to creating accommodations after barriers were identified, the ES team designed materials to provide multiple means of engagement, representation, and action from the start.

Accessibility was addressed at three interconnected levels:

- Physical kit design
- Device modification
- Instructional delivery

Together, these elements supported blind and low vision (BLV) volunteers and benefited all Data Collectors by providing redundant, multisensory access to information and device operation.

Accessible Instructions

Each Data Collection Kit included a business card–sized instruction card linking participants to the Data Collector Role requirements, setup steps, and training resources. The card displayed the website address in large print, in Braille, and included a QR code.

This design choice reflected both accessibility and UDL considerations:

- **Multiple means of representation:** Participants could access instructions through print, Braille, or digital formats.
- **Reduced cognitive load:** Rather than navigating lengthy printed manuals, participants were directed to a centralized, structured online training hub.
- **Iterative improvement:** Digital access allowed the ES team to update instructions in real time without re-mailing materials.
- **Cost-awareness:** The approach ensured accessibility without the financial burden of producing full-length large-print and Braille manuals for every kit.

This system ensured that all participants had access to the most current guidance while maintaining inclusive access.

AudioMoth Accessibility and Multisensory Design

To support independent participation by blind and low vision volunteers and others who benefit from tactile references, ES modified the AudioMoth devices and developed structured multisensory instructional supports.

Device modifications included:

- A unique ES ID number printed in both Braille and large print
- Distinct tactile bump dots placed near key components
- Consistent orientation cues for locating switches and ports

These modifications were not merely accommodations. They were integrated into the instructional design itself. The tactile system became part of the standardized training for all participants, ensuring consistent device orientation across deployments and supporting reliable data collection.

By embedding tactile landmarks into both the physical device and the instructional language, ES created alignment between hardware design and training scaffolding. This alignment reduced reliance on vision-only cues while maintaining standardized deployment procedures across all users.

ES ID Accessibility and Durable Labeling

The ES ID system was designed with both accessibility and long-term durability in mind.

Each three-digit ES ID was added in:

- Large print on the AudioMoth device
- Braille on the AudioMoth device
- Large print on the device box
- Braille on the device box

Initial efforts focused on labeling the device itself. However, over time, Braille labels attached directly to the AudioMoth were not durable, even when secured with strong adhesive. To ensure long-term reliability, the ES team also added the ES ID in both large print and Braille to the cardboard device box. The box surface provided a more effective and durable labeling location.

This dual-labeling approach allowed participants to access their ES ID in multiple ways. Participants who do not read Braille and cannot read large print may use mobile accessibility tools, such as camera-based text readers (e.g., Lookout by Google or similar applications), to read the ES ID aloud.

By providing the ES ID in multiple ways, ES supported independent participant identification of devices while preserving accurate linkage between audio files, metadata submissions, and archived datasets.

This approach reflects Eclipse Soundscapes' commitment to Universal Design principles by providing multiple ways to access critical device information while maintaining usability, traceability, and data integrity.

Participant Accessible Device Instructions

Participants received AudioMoth training materials designed in accordance with UDL best practices. Instruction was delivered through:

- Text descriptions
- Visual diagrams
- Video demonstrations
- Tactile orientation guidance

This multimodal structure ensured that participants with different sensory preferences and access needs could engage fully and independently. The following training text was provided directly to ES Data Collectors and is preserved verbatim.

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Get to Know your AudioMoth with a Bump Dots Tour

This is the AudioMoth Bump Dots Tour. Please pick up your AudioMoth recording device and follow along to take a tactile tour of the device's components. As you read, hold the AudioMoth and feel for the parts being described.

AudioMoth Bottom

The bottom of your AudioMoth has a plastic battery case or holder with an opening for 3 AA batteries. You shouldn't insert the batteries until you are ready to set up the AudioMoth 1-2 weeks before the eclipse.

AudioMoth Top

The top of your AudioMoth is a thin credit-card-sized metal circuit board attached to the plastic battery holder. This circuit board has 3 rubbery silicone bump dots attached to it; one large square with a flat top, one large circle with a flat top, and one small circle with a rounded top. You might also feel some of the metal circuitry bumps and grooves on the top of the AudioMoth.

Don't worry about these smaller circuitry elements. We will focus on using the 3 rubbery bump dots as guides to help us find important parts of this device.

Orient the AudioMoth

To orient your AudioMoth before looking for a switch or port, you should always start by placing your AudioMoth battery side down. Then feel around on the top of the circuit board for the large square bump dot. The square bump dot should be positioned in the top left corner.

The Switch

With the square bump dot positioned at the top left, find the small circle bump dot with the rounded top near the bottom edge. The switch is along the bottom edge next to the rounded bump dot. Feel the along the side edge of the circuit board near the rounded bump dot. There is an indent or divot along that edge. The tiny switch is located just below that divot in between the

circuit board and the plastic battery case. You might have to run your finger nail along that divot to find the tiny switch.

The switch has 3 settings: Custom, USB/Off, and Default. Custom is closest to the bump dot. USB/Off is in the middle. Default is furthest away from the bump dot.

For now you will need to set the switch on “USB/Off,” which is the middle setting. On the day that you leave your AudioMoth to record eclipse data, you will set this switch on “default,” which is the setting furthest away from the small circle bump dot to start recording.

Micro-SD Card

With the square bump dot positioned at the top left, the MicroSd card port is located on the top edge near the square bump dot. The top circuit board edge has indents. The MicroSD card port is in between the circuit board edge and the plastic battery holder directly next to the square bump dot. When a MicroSD card is inserted it sticks out a little. When you push on an inserted MicroSD card it will click and partially pop out. You do NOT want to remove the MicroSD card. You should push the

MicroSD back into the device. You will hear a click when you push the MicroSD card back into the device. [If you receive an AudioMoth from the ES team, it will have MicroSd card already installed. Purchased AudioMoth do NOT come with a MicroSD card.]

Mini USB Port

With the square bump dot positioned in the top left, the Micro USB port is on the top edge. Feel for the large circle bump dot with the flat top. Feel for the indent on the edge of the circuit board directly above the round bump dot with the flat top. The Micro USB port is located within that indent in between the plastic battery case and the circuit board. You won't need to use the Micro USB port

for this project, but it is good to know where it is for future use!

Facilitator Professional Development: Modeling Inclusive Design

ES also provided professional development resources explaining how and why tactile bump dots were used to improve device accessibility. These materials were intended for ES partners, educators, library staff, and other facilitators interested in inclusive design methods.

By documenting and sharing the tactile modification process, ES extended accessibility beyond individual kits and modeled scalable inclusive design practices that could be adopted in other educational and participatory science contexts.

The video resource below demonstrates this approach in practice. The video, and the accompanying text that was distributed with the video, are preserved here for archival accuracy.

Video:

Severino, M. (2026, February 11). *Inclusive Design in Practice: Making the AudioMoth Tactilely Accessible with Bump Dots*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18615035>

Participant-Facing Facilitator Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Making the AudioMoth Tactilely Accessible with Bump Dots

Have you ever wondered how someone who is blind or has low-vision (BLV) knows which button is which on the microwave or the washing machine? For many, it is with the help of “Bump Dots!” Bump dots are silicone stickers that come in various shapes, sizes, and colors. They are a very common household item, used to keep cabinet doors and drawers from slamming, as non-slip feet on vases, etc. They can also be used as tactile cues on devices to create tactile, or touch, cues to make that device more tactilely accessible.

The Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) team added clear bump dots of different shapes to the AudioMoth recording device to make it easier to find the important ports and the switch by feel. ES Data Collectors will use an AudioMoth device to record audio data, known as soundscapes, for 5 consecutive days during either the October 14, 2023 annular eclipse or the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse. Below you can learn more about where we added these bump dots so you can add some too if you purchased your own AudioMoth device!

Eclipse Soundscapes Identification Number (ES ID)

What Is an ES ID?

Each AudioMoth device contains a unique 16-character serial number embedded in its firmware. This serial number is automatically written into every audio file the device records.

To connect mailed audio files with participant-submitted online metadata, Eclipse Soundscapes needed a reliable identifier. While the embedded serial number provided accurate technical traceability, it was long and difficult for participants to enter correctly in online forms.

To simplify participation and reduce transcription errors, the ES team created the Eclipse Soundscapes Identification Number (ES ID), a unique three-digit number assigned to each AudioMoth's serial number. Participants entered the ES ID in online forms, while the project team maintained the secure internal spreadsheet linking the ES IDs with their full device serial numbers.

The ES ID system allowed:

- Volunteers to enter a short, three-digit number in online forms
- The ES team to link mailed microSD cards to online location data
- Automated systems to connect ES IDs to embedded AudioMoth serial numbers

The ES team maintained a secure internal spreadsheet linking each ES ID to its corresponding AudioMoth serial number. This ensured accurate matching of:

- Mailed audio files
- Device serial numbers embedded in recordings
- Online location and deployment metadata

The ES ID system simplified participation while maintaining data integrity and traceability.

How ES IDs Connect Audio and Location Data

When Data Collectors mailed their microSD cards:

1. The ES team extracted the AudioMoth serial number directly from the audio files.
2. The participant-submitted ES ID (entered online) was matched to that serial number.
3. The ES ID linked the audio files to the correct geographic location and metadata.

As long as the ES ID was correctly entered in the online form, the audio recordings could always be linked to the correct site information.

ES ID Registration Process

To participate as a Data Collector, each AudioMoth device required a registered ES ID number. Devices distributed by the ES team or ES partners already had ES IDs assigned. Individuals using personally purchased AudioMoth devices were required to register online to receive a unique ES ID. Registration required participants to be 13 years of age or older and included submission of an email address, zip code, and the device's serial number.

The ES ID Registration Form automatically assigned a unique three-digit ES ID and delivered it to the participant via email. Accurate ES ID registration was essential for linking mailed audio data to submitted site metadata.

Public Archiving, Privacy, and Data Transparency

Public archiving of audio data was disclosed to participants in advance as a core deliverable of the Eclipse Soundscapes project. The project's open data commitment was communicated:

- In role descriptions and training materials,
- During ES ID registration,
- In metadata submission instructions,
- In guidance regarding microSD return.

Participants were informed that recordings meeting archival standards, accurate location information and non-corrupted audio files, would be shared publicly on Zenodo as site-level records organized by ES ID number.

The ES ID system was designed to support both transparency and privacy. Rather than associating recordings with participant names, the project used a unique three-digit ES ID to connect:

- The AudioMoth device,
- The embedded serial number in the audio files,
- The participant-submitted metadata,
- The publicly archived Zenodo record.

This approach allowed:

- Accurate technical traceability of each dataset,
- Public sharing of site-level recordings without publishing personal identifiers,
- Participants to easily locate their own data in the public archive using their ES ID.

By separating participant identity from public data while preserving site-level traceability, the ES ID system supported open science principles while maintaining appropriate privacy protections.

Participant ES ID Website Content (2023–2024)

The following text and image descriptions were provided directly to ES Data Collectors via the project website. This language is preserved verbatim for archival accuracy.

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Unique ES ID Number

Data Collectors will mail their MicroSD card with its audio data to the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) team. For such a large file of data, mailing rather than uploading was determined to be the best option for time and cost reasons. But, how does the ES team know where that data came from?

A unique ES ID# will connect the Audio data you mail with the location information you enter online!

Each MicroSD card has the AudioMoth’s serial number embedded within its data. So when we receive the data we know which AudioMoth recorded the data. However, AudioMoth serial numbers are really long. It would be too long for a Data Collector to type into an online form. Instead, we assign each AudioMoth a shorter and unique ES ID#. Each ES ID# is 3 digits long and this ES ID# is linked to the AudioMoth’s serial number.

As long as you always include your ES ID# in the location information you enter online, we can always link your MicroSd card data to the online location info that you submitted!

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Determining Your ES ID# Depends on Where You Got Your AudioMoth

Option 1: Received AudioMoth from ES team or partners

If you received an AudioMoth from the ES team, you already have an ES ID#! Follow the instructions below to learn where find your ES ID#.

Option 2: Purchased My AudioMoth

If you purchased an AudioMoth to participate, just follow the instructions below to register your AudioMoth for a unique ES ID#.

Option 1 Instructions (AudioMoth Received from ES Team or partners)

Where to find your ES ID#?

If you received your AudioMoth from the ES team, or one of its partners, then your AudioMoth has already been registered and assigned a unique ES ID#. The ES ID# is a 3 digit number that is located on the AudioMoth box in braille and large print. The ES ID# is also printed on the device itself in the bottom right corner.

AudioMoth box: ES ID 001

AudioMoth Device: ES ID 001

Option 2 Instructions (AudioMoth Purchased / NOT from ES Team or partners)

How to Register Your AudioMoth to Receive a Unique ES ID#

If you purchased your AudioMoth you will need to register your AudioMoth device to receive a unique ES ID#. Follow the steps to first find your AudioMoth's serial number and then fill out the form. You MUST be 13 years or older to register for an ED ID#. The form will require your email address, zip code, and AudioMoth serial number. After you submit the form, you will be emailed your unique ES ID#. We recommend writing the ES ID# on your AudioMoth device and on the AudioMoth box.

Step 1: Find your AudioMoth's Serial Number

- Download the [AudioMoth configuration App](https://www.openacousticdevices.info/applications) <https://www.openacousticdevices.info/applications> to your computer
- Attach your AudioMoth to your computer using a USB cord
- Open the "AudioMoth Configuration App"
- The "Device ID" will be listed at the top on the right. This is the AudioMoth serial number. You will need to enter this series of numbers and letters in step 2 to register your AudioMoth for an ES ID#.
- Disconnect your AudioMoth. No other steps are needed with this app for eclipse soundscapes data collection.

Step 2: Register your AudioMoth via the form below

Fill out the form below to register your AudioMoth recorder to receive your Eclipse Soundscapes Identification number (ES ID #). Your ES ID # will be immediately emailed to you. If you do not receive an email with your ES ID# please email info@EclipseSoundscapes.org.

Enter Email
user@email.com

Enter Zip Code
XXXXX

Enter AudioMoth Serial Number
XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX

REGISTER

Training Webinars

ES Data Collectors attended or watched a recording of a training webinar to learn:

- Why are we recording audio data?
- What kind of audio data is helpful?
- ES Data Collector equipment & materials
- Where to record audio data / put the AudioMoth
- How long to record audio data
- How to prepare the AudioMoth
- What notes to take about the data recording location
- How to submit the audio data

Recordings of these webinars and Q&A office hours are included in:

- Severino, M., & Winter, H. (2026). Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Role Training and Implementation Manual (2023–2024). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623443>

Asynchronous Training & Instructions

In addition to the AudioMoth device training, Section: [Get to Know your AudioMoth with a Bump Dots Tour](#), and ES ID training, Section: [Participant ES ID Website Content \(2023–2024\)](#), provided earlier in this manual, the following additional asynchronous training modules were made publicly available on the Eclipse Soundscapes website during the 2023 and 2024 eclipse cycles. These modules supported independent preparation, equipment setup, metadata accuracy, and data return, and formed the procedural backbone of the ES Data Collector role.

The same content informed live and recorded training webinars and structured, time-relevant role-specific email communications. The lessons below are preserved verbatim to document the exact participant-facing instructional language used during project implementation.

1. [Choosing a data collection site](#)
2. [AudioMoth preparation](#)
3. [How to set the AudioMoth clock using a time chime](#)
4. [AudioMoth flashing instructions](#)
5. [Eclipse week data collection instructions](#)
6. [Solar Eclipse Safety](#)
7. [How to find & format Latitude and Longitude \(DD Format\)](#)
8. [Post eclipse week data submission instructions](#)

1. Choosing a data collection site

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

How to Choose an AudioMoth Deployment Location

Data Collectors can deploy devices in urban, suburban, and rural environments, or wherever they expect insect, bird, or animal activity.

Recordings help explore:

- Do daytime species become quieter during an eclipse?
- Do nocturnal species increase in activity?

ES encourages participants to use [iNaturalist](#) resources to find a recording site. (<https://www.inaturalist.org>)

Learn More about the Animals & Insects in your Area with iNaturalist

Are you curious about where you can find crickets or other animals and insects in your area? Do you wonder what animals and insects in your area look and sound like? Check out what animals and insects [iNaturalist observers](#) have found in your area so you know what to look and listen for on eclipse day!

(https://www.inaturalist.org/observations?place_id=any&subview=map)

2. AudioMoth preparation

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

AudioMoth Preparation

Preparation steps depend on the kit type:

- **2024 ES Kit:** Batteries and clock pre-installed; confirm flashing red light to verify clock.
- **2023 ES Kit:** Insert batteries and MicroSD card, then reset clock.
- **Self-Purchased Device:** Flash firmware, insert 64 GB card, install batteries, set clock, and register for an ES ID #.

All recorders used the default continuous recording configuration (48 kHz sampling rate, medium gain). You can learn more about all of the steps below:

AudioMoth Preparation Done before Deployment Day

The Eclipse Soundscapes team requires volunteers to use the AudioMoth's default setting to record (48kHz and medium gain with continuous recording). No custom settings are required.

The set-up instructions for the AudioMoth differed based on whether the volunteer received an ES Data Collector kit from the ES Team in 2024, Received a kit from the ES team in 2023, or purchased an AudioMoth device. The different set-up instructions for each are below.

Received a Kit from the ES Team in 2024

All ES Data Collector kits that were provided in 2024 include AudioMoths with already installed batteries and the clocks already set. You must confirm that the clock is set by following the steps below.

Ensure the Clock is Set:

Embedded Video:

Severino, M. (2026, February 11). Eclipse Soundscapes Training: How to Check to See if AudioMoth Clock is set (Data Collector Role). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18614322>

1. Move the switch to the “custom” position.

2. If a red light flashes continuously on the edge where the MicroSD port is located, the clock is set.
3. Move the switch back to the “USB/Off” mode until you deploy the AudioMoth.

Troubleshooting:

- If there is a green light or a solid red light, you will need to set the clock again.
- If the batteries have been removed, you will need to set the clock again.

When your AudioMoth clock is set, it is ready for deployment. Keep the switch on “USB/OFF” until you deploy the AudioMoth. The AudioMoth will not record in the “USB/Off” mode.

Received a Kit from the ES Team in 2023

Returning Data Collectors who will use their 2023 Data Collector kit to record audio data again in 2024 will need to follow the steps below to get their AudioMoth ready to record data again.

2023 kit)

1. Install 3 new AA batteries (extras were included in the

your 2023 kit)

2. Install a new MicroSD card (extra was included in

batteries and MicroSD card.

3. Set the AudioMoth clock after installing

After completing the above steps, your AudioMoth is ready for deployment. Keep the switch on “USB/OFF” until you deploy the AudioMoth. The AudioMoth will not record in the “USB/Off” mode.

Purchased an AudioMoth

If you purchased an AudioMoth, you will need to follow the steps below to get your device all set up.

1. Flash your AudioMoth with Firmware

2. Install a 64 GB Extreme U3 MicroSDXC card

3. Install 3 new AA batteries

[AudioMoth flashing instructions Training](#)

4. Set the AudioMoth clock after installing batteries and MicroSD card.

[How to set the AudioMoth clock using a time chime Training](#)

5. Register for a Unique ES ID#.

[ES ID Info and registration](#)

After completing the above steps, your AudioMoth is ready for deployment. Keep the switch on “USB/OFF” until you deploy the AudioMoth. The AudioMoth will not record in the “USB/Off” mode.

AudioMoth Configuration: The Eclipse Soundscapes team is using the AudioMoth’s default setting to record (48kHz and medium gain with continuous recording). “Enable sleep/record cyclic recording” is OFF in the DEFAULT state. You do not need to set up any custom settings. If you have previously adjusted your AudioMoth’s configuration, please return the settings to this default.

3. How to set the AudioMoth clock using a time chime

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Setting the AudioMoth Clock

In order for the audio data you record to have a time stamp with the current time and date, AudioMoth devices must keep track of the current time. When the batteries are removed and power to the device is lost, it is unable to keep track of the time and resets to 01/01/1970 at 00:00. For this reason, whenever the batteries are removed from your device, you must connect set the clock using an acoustic chime. The AudioMoth has LED lights that assist users in understanding if the clock has been set. There are two options for accessing the acoustic chime. You can use the button below on this webpage in step 5 or you can [download AudioMoth Chime App](#). Follow the steps below to set the clock using whichever time chime option you choose. (<https://www.openacousticdevices.info/mobileapplications>)

Accessibility Considerations

The Eclipse Soundscapes Team has added tactile bump dots to the AudioMoths it distributes to support accessibility. Unfortunately the ES team has not determined a way to set the AudioMoth's clock in a way that doesn't require both audio and visual cues. We hope that participants can work together with friends, family, and community to complete this step of the AudioMoth set-up. The ES team also asks that Data Collectors write down the time at which they start the data recording and enter it in the online form about location. This way if the clock is not set correctly for any reason, no need to worry, there is a back up!

AudioMoth Not Received from ES Team

If you purchased your own AudioMoth, please make sure to follow the steps to flash your AudioMoth in order to install firmware before setting the AudioMoth's clock or this process will not work. [AudioMoth flashing instructions](#)

Setting Clock with Time Chime Instructions

Embedded Video:

Severino, M. (2026, February 11). Eclipse Soundscapes Training: How to set the time chime on your AudioMoth device (Data Collector Role). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18614955>

1. Install the 3 AA batteries in your AudioMoth

After you set the AudioMoth clock, you cannot remove the batteries. If the batteries are removed, you must follow these steps again to set the time. You can turn the AudioMoth off AFTER you follow these steps to set the clock. Turning the AudioMoth off is the last step in this process.

2. Now move the switch to the "custom" position.

3. The AudioMoth will indicate the clock is NOT set and it is ready with lights

When the clock is NOT set, the Green light flashes and the red light is steady.

4. Make sure the volume of your device is turned up loud

5. Place or hold the AudioMoth near the speaker of your device or computer and press the time chime button below or from the mobile app.

Time Chime (*Button linked to audio chime*)

The button will play a chime twice. It will chime once, briefly pause, then play again. The mobile App will only play the chime once. It might take a few chimes to get the clock set.

Lights While Clock Sets: While the clock is setting the green light will flash faster, and then hold steady for a few seconds and the red light will go dark. Then both lights will turn off, and then both will flash. When just the red light is flashing, the clock is set.

Step 6. Check your AudioMoth's lights to determine if the clock is set

Clock IS Set

With switch on “CUSTOM,” the red light will flash if the clock is set.

Clock is NOT Set

With switch on “CUSTOM,” the red light will be on and steady and the green light will flash if the clock is NOT set.

7. After clock is set, Move the Switch to “USB/OFF”

While in “USB/OFF” mode, the AudioMoth will not record and will use less battery power. It will also not lose the clock settings. If you remove the batteries, you will have to set the clock again.

Troubleshooting

Before the AudioMoths were sent out by the ES team they were flashed with 1.8.1 firmware. This should add a generic recording schedule in the “Custom mode.” We won’t be using this generic schedule as Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collectors will record using “default mode” to record one continuous recording until turned off. But this generic recording schedule should allow for the time clock to be set as the instructions above outline. However, sometimes there are technical glitches. So, here are some steps to try:

- If the time setting process does not work, remove the batteries for a few minutes and try again.
- Flash the AudioMoth with firmware update 1.8.1
- Check out [Open Acoustic Devices Support Forum](https://www.openacousticdevices.info/support) (https://www.openacousticdevices.info/support)
- Post a question on the EclipseSoundscapes FB page

If none of the above troubleshooting steps above work:

1. Confirm that the AudioMoth records when in “default mode.” To do this move switch to default mode and make there is a flashing red light. Then flip switch back to “off/USB” until deployment.
2. When deploying, write down the exact minute that you turn the AudioMoth to record. To turn AudioMoth to record you move the switch to “default mode.”
3. There is a place to add recording start time in the location notes form on the Data Collector page that Data Collectors fill out after collecting data.

4. Mail the MicroSD AND the AudioMoth back to us after the eclipse in the padded envelope. Add a note with start/end recording times, latitude and longitude, and your mailing address so we can mail you a new AudioMoth. This will allow us to manually tag the time on your collected data and also ensure that you have an AudioMoth that you can use a different one for the next 2024 eclipse.

Thank you for your patience, effort, and participation. We appreciate your involvement in NASA eclipse science!

Safeguard / Back-up Plan

The ES team also asks that Data Collectors write down the time at which they start the data recording and enter it in the online form about location. This way if the clock is not set correctly for any reason, no need to worry, there is a back up! The ES team can use what a Data Collector enters as the recording start time to manually adjust the audio file start time.

4. AudioMoth flashing instructions

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

AudioMoth Flashing Instructions

If you received an AudioMoth from the Eclipse Soundscapes team or one of our partners, you do NOT need to flash your AudioMoth. Your AudioMoth was already flashed with the necessary firmware by the ES team. This step is only for ES participants who purchased their own AudioMoth.

AudioMoth devices need to have the firmware update to properly set the AudioMoth’s clock with the Time Chime. This page explains how to download the firmware. So that all AudioMoths are flashed with the same firmware update, we are asking participants to use version 1.8.1 or 1.8.2

Install your MicroSD card before you flash your AudioMoth

AudioMoth Flash App

The AudioMoth Flash App is used to easily flash your AudioMoth with the latest firmware. Keep your AudioMoth up to date by downloading and applying firmware through this app.

It can also be used to flash devices with your own custom firmware.

Download:

Current version: 1.4.1

Step 1: Download the AudioMoth Flash Application

Visit

<https://www.openacousticdevices.info/applications> to download the “AudioMoth Flash App.” The Flash app is the second app on the webpage.

Step 2: Follow your computer's instructions to install the application.

Step 3: Open the AudioMoth Flash Application

Step 4: Select firmware version 1.8.1 in the menu on the right and click on the download button.

Step 5: Insert the MicroSD card into your AudioMoth, Move AudioMoth Switch to USB/Off, & Connect AudioMoth via USB micro-b cable to your computer

You can connect the AudioMoth with or without batteries. When connected, the light on AudioMoth should be a solid green.

(Tip: the AudioMoth can be finicky. Sometimes you have to try a few different cords until you find one that recognizes the AudioMoth, even when the cord works fine with other devices)

Step 6: Click the "Flash AudioMoth" button. The button will become clickable when the AudioMoth is connected to your computer. The text above the green "Flash AudioMoth" button will also change from "No AudioMoth found" to "Found an AudioMoth..."

Step 7: Flashing will take a few minutes and the app should let you know once it is complete. Once complete, you can disconnect the AudioMoth.

Reminders!

- Don't forget to set the AudioMoth clock after flashing your AudioMoth!
 - [How to set the AudioMoth clock using a time chime Training](#)
- Don't forget to register your AudioMoth with Eclipse Soundscapes!
 - [ES ID Info and registration](#)

5. Eclipse week data collection instructions

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Eclipse Week Data Collection Instructions Explained

Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collectors recorded soundscapes during two solar eclipses:

- **2023 Annular Solar Eclipse** (October 14 2023): Data Collectors deploy AudioMoths from October 12 – 16, 2023, capturing the unique sound changes that occur as the Moon covered most of the Sun but left a "ring of fire." Recordings from this event form the first phase of the ES soundscape dataset and helped refine the training, deployment, and upload process used the following year.

- **2024 Total Solar Eclipse (April 8 2024):** For the total eclipse, Data Collectors record from April 6 – 10, 2024, capturing soundscapes before, during, and after totality across the eclipse path from Mexico to Maine.

Deploy AudioMoth (BEFORE noon)

Secure device outside 2 days before the eclipse. Place AudioMoth in plastic bag for waterproofing. Secure with zip ties and face circuit board out, batteries against surface.

1. Set switch to “Default” to start recording.
2. Take Location Notes
 - recording start time
 - latitude & longitude (DD)
 - location info: urban? rural? near road or river? etc

Leave Device for 5 days

Retrieve AudioMoth (AFTER 5pm)

2 days after the eclipse.

- Set switch to “USB/Off” to stop recording
- Write the time you stopped recording

Submit Recording Location Notes Online

ES ID#, Latitude & longitude (DD), start/stop recording time, & location info.

SUBMIT LOCATION INFO

(Button directed to Online location information survey)

6. Solar Eclipse Safety

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Solar Eclipse Safety

As an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector, your activities happen before and after eclipse day. So you are free to experience the eclipse on eclipse day as you'd like – perhaps as an ES Observer! It's very important that safety is your highest priority during any ES activity and on eclipse day. Please review the safety information below. If you took the Apprentice Training, this will be a review. If you did not take the Apprentice Training, it is a good idea to do that before being an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector!

Eye safety is very important during solar eclipses! Sunglasses WILL NOT protect your eyes. You also CANNOT look through a telescope or camera without a special solar filter. If you want to look at the Sun during a solar eclipse you MUST wear special eclipse glasses or use a special eclipse viewer. There is one eclipse safety difference between the total solar eclipse and all the other solar eclipse types. Please keep reading to learn the difference and stay safe! (<https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety/optics-filters>)

Annular Eclipse Safety (Oct 14, 2023)

(Embedded Video: *What Is an Annular Eclipse?* | NASA Goddard, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sNBbMWkSlh4>)

Video Time: 1:13-1:44 of this video will play for this lesson.

You CANNOT look at the sun without eclipse glasses or a solar filter during an annular solar eclipse, such as the one on October 14, 2023. There is NO time when it is safe to look directly at the Sun without wearing eclipse glasses or using a special solar filter.

You must make sure you have official eclipse glasses or the correct solar filter. Please visit the American Astronomical Society website for up-to-date and accurate information on suppliers of safe eclipse glasses and filters. (Eclipse Safety information: <https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety>)

Total Solar Eclipse Safety (April 8, 2024)

(Embedded Video: *Solar Eclipse 101* | National Geographic, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cxrLRbkOwKs>)

Video Time: 2:32-4:20 of this video will play for this lesson.

A total solar eclipse has 5 phases. There is ONLY one phase when you can remove your eclipse glasses briefly while looking at the Sun. During the maximum phase of a total solar eclipse you can take off your eclipse glasses briefly because the entire Sun is blocked from view. The maximum phase is called totality. Totality is when the Moon entirely blocks the Sun's bright surface. This happens for only a few minutes during a total solar eclipse. (Eclipse Safety information: <https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety>)

Partial Solar Eclipse Safety

If you are NOT on the eclipse path on October 14, 2023 or April 8, 2024 you will experience a partial eclipse. There is NO time when it is safe to look directly at the Sun without wearing eclipse glasses or a solar filter during a partial solar eclipse. You CANNOT look at the sun without eclipse glasses or a solar filter. (<https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety/optics-filters>)

You must make sure you have official eclipse glasses or the correct solar filter. Please visit the American Astronomical Society website for up-to-date and accurate information on suppliers of safe eclipse glasses and filters. (Eclipse Safety information: <https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety>)

Vocabulary

- **annular eclipse** – when the Moon passes directly in front of the Sun, but appears to be too small to completely block the Sun
- maximum phase – the phase of an eclipse when the Moon is lined up with the Sun
- **partial solar eclipse** – when the Moon passes in front of the Sun off-center and does not block the surface
- **solar filter** – a filter added on to a camera or telescope that blocks out most of the Sun's light to allow the user to look at the Sun
- **total solar eclipse** – when the Moon passes directly in front of the Sun completely blocking the Sun from view

Discussion / Notes

Write, draw, or verbally discuss the answers to the following:

- During which phase of a total solar eclipse is it ok to take off your eclipse glasses?
 - Is it ever safe to take off your eclipse glasses during an annular eclipse?
 - Is it ever safe to take off your eclipse glasses during a partial solar eclipse?
 - Who will experience a partial eclipse on October 14, 2023 and April 8, 2024?
-

Bonus Activity: Make a Pinhole Projector

- *How to Make a Pinhole Camera* | NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology (<https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/edu/learn/project/how-to-make-a-pinhole-camera>)

- *How to make a pinhole projector to view the solar eclipse* | CNET, (<https://www.cnet.com/science/how-to-make-a-pinhole-projector-to-view-the-eclipse/>)
- *Projection: Pinhole & Optical* | American Astronomical Society, (<https://eclipse.aas.org/eye-safety/projection>)

7. How to find & format Latitude and Longitude (DD Format)

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

How to find Latitude and Longitude (DD Format)

Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Observers and Data Collectors need to report their location using latitude and longitude. Latitude and longitude have different formats. ES uses Decimal Degrees (DD) format. Please record at least 5 decimal places. Below is some information and resources to help you find your latitude and longitude and make sure it is in the correct format.

Latitude and Longitude with Google Maps

Computer

1. On your computer, open [Google Maps](https://www.google.com/maps) (<https://www.google.com/maps>).
2. Right-click the place or area on the map.
 - This will open a pop-up window. You can find your latitude and longitude in decimal format at the top.
3. To copy the coordinates automatically, left click on the latitude and longitude

Reference Link:

<https://support.google.com/maps/answer/18539?hl=en&co=GENIE.Platform%3DDesktop>

Android Phone or Tablet

1. On your Android phone or tablet, open the Google Maps application.
2. Touch and hold an area of the map that isn't labeled to drop a red pin.
3. In the search box, you can find the coordinates.

Reference Link:

<https://support.google.com/maps/answer/18539?hl=en&co=GENIE.Platform%3DAndroid&oco=1>

iPhone or iPad

1. On your iPhone or iPad, open the Google Maps application.
2. Touch and hold an area of the map that isn't labeled to drop a red pin.
3. At the bottom, tap Dropped pin to find the coordinates.

Reference Link:

<https://support.google.com/maps/answer/18539?hl=en&co=GENIE.Platform%3DiOS&oco=1>

Format Your Latitude and Longitude Coordinates

To format your coordinates so they work with the Observer and Data Collector online forms, use decimal degrees (DD) in the following format:

- Correct: 41.40338, 2.17403
- Incorrect: 41,40338, 2,17403

Tips:

- List your latitude coordinates before your longitude coordinates.
- Check that the first number in your latitude coordinate is between -90 and 90.
- Check that the first number in your longitude coordinate is between -180 and 180.

8. Post eclipse week data submission instructions

Participant-Facing Training Content (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Data Submission

Step 1: Submit Recording Location Information

Participants entered their device ES ID#, Latitude & longitude (DD), start/stop recording time, & any other location info and notes via an online form.

Step 2: Mail your Data to the ES Team

Data Collectors mailed their MicroSD cards and notes, including the data recording location, latitude & longitude, and recording start time. MicroSD cards will NOT be returned to participants after submission.

Mail MicroSD Card and field notes to:

ES Team c/o ARISA Lab, 47 High Street Ste 501, Medford MA 02155

Implementation Note on Online Submission Forms (2023–2024)

In 2023, the Recording Location Information form was administered using the Alchemer platform. In 2024, the form was administered using Qualtrics. Both versions collected structured field notes including ES ID number, latitude and longitude in Decimal Degrees (DD), recording start and stop times, deployment site descriptions, and microSD card return confirmation. Submission of this form served as official completion of the ES Data Collector role and triggered certificate access. Documentation of both the 2023 and 2024 submission forms are preserved in the *Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Role Training and Implementation Manual* Zenodo record (Severino & Winter, 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623443>).

Ongoing Email Support and Communication Timeline

Structured Email Support

In addition to live and recorded webinars and asynchronous training materials, the Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) team provided email communications to support ES Data Collectors throughout each of the eclipses.

During the 2023 annular eclipse cycle, participants received general project updates and reminders. However, communications were not structured or delivered as role-specific messages for Data Collectors.

Based on participant feedback and internal reflection following the 2023 eclipse, the ES team implemented a structured, role-specific email communication timeline for the 2024 total solar eclipse cycle. Anyone interested in participating as a Data Collector was invited to sign up for role specific reminders via a Google Form.

- *Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Sign Up - Google form 2024* ([Appendix 3](#))

These messages were intentionally aligned with training modules and deployment milestones and were scheduled to reinforce key actions at time-relevant intervals.

The goals of this structured communication approach were to:

- Reinforce training content over time
- Provide clear procedural reminders tied to deployment stages
- Reduce cognitive load by pacing information delivery
- Increase participant confidence in equipment setup and data return
- Improve consistency in metadata reporting

This approach reflects ES's commitment to Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles by providing multiple, spaced representations of essential information rather than relying on a single exposure during initial training.

2024 Email Communication Timeline

The following timeline summarizes the structured, role-specific email sequence sent exclusively to registered ES Data Collectors during the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse cycle. These communications were aligned with Data Collector training modules and deployment milestones and were separate from general project-wide updates.

Date	Topic	Purpose
2/18/2024	Eclipse Safety	Reinforce safe eclipse viewing practices
2/25/2024	What is the AudioMoth?	Reintroduce the recording device and its scientific purpose
3/3/2024	What makes a good Data collection location?	Guide site selection for optimal sound capture
3/10/2024	Latitude & longitude	Ensure accurate reporting of latitude & longitude
3/17/2024	Setting up you AudioMoth	Provide setup instructions and clock verification guidance
4/1/2024	Planning Deployment	Support scheduling and logistical preparation
4/3/2024	Deploy in 3 days & Checklist	Countdown reminder, waterproofing, & checklist
4/4/2024	Deploy in 2 days	Reinforce recording start procedures
4/5/2024	Deploy tomorrow	Final deployment checklist and troubleshooting reminder
4/9/2024	Collect your AudioMoth	Remind retrieval and documentation of end time
4/11/2024	Submit your data	Prompt microSD mailing and online form completion

Resources

Based on feedback from partners and volunteer scientists who participated in 2023 as Data Collectors, we created the following resources for participants to use in 2024 further demonstrating commitment to participant-focused iterative design.

- **Printable *Data Collector Checklists*** : Each checklist differed slightly depending on whether a Data Collector was re-using a 2023 kit provided by ES, using a 2024 kit provided by ES, or using a kit put together by the volunteer scientist on their own. As a result several different checklists were created. They were also provided in English and Spanish.
 - Re-Using 2023 ES Kit Checklist [English] ([Appendix 4](#))
 - Using 2024 ES Kit Checklist [English] ([Appendix 5](#))
 - Using Personal Kit Checklist [English] ([Appendix 6](#))
 - Re-Using 2023 ES Kit Checklist [Spanish] ([Appendix 7](#))
 - Using 2024 ES Kit Checklist [Spanish] ([Appendix 8](#))
 - Using Personal Kit Checklist [Spanish] ([Appendix 9](#))
- **Printable *Science Experiment in Progress* label** for the AudioMoth to be added to the device's package while left in the field recording for people who put together their own kit.

Certificate and SciStarter Credit

Certificate of Completion

Volunteer scientists who participated in Eclipse Soundscapes as ES Data Collectors received an ES Data Collector Certificate of Completion after submitting the required Data Collector form. In 2023, the form was administered through Alchemer, and in 2024 through Qualtrics. In both years, certificate access was integrated directly into the submission workflow.

To complete the ES Data Collector role, participants were required to submit the online form, which included recording site location, participant-entered latitude and longitude, recording start and end times, additional deployment field notes, and confirmation of microSD card return status. In 2023, this submission form was administered using the Alchemer platform. In 2024, the form was administered using Qualtrics. Both versions of the form collected structured field notes, including ES ID number, latitude and longitude in Decimal Degrees (DD), recording start and stop times, deployment location descriptions, and microSD card return confirmation. Documentation for both the 2023 (Alchemer) and 2024 (Qualtrics) forms are preserved in the *Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Role Training and Implementation Manual* Zenodo record (Severino & Winter, 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623443>).

At the beginning of the form, participants indicated whether they were 13 years of age or older or under 13 years of age. Certificate delivery options were determined by this selection.

Participants who indicated they were 13 years of age or older were given two options after submission:

- View and print the certificate directly from the screen
- Enter their name and email address to receive a personalized certificate via email

Participants who indicated they were under 13 years of age were not given the option to enter a name or email address. Instead, they were provided a printable certificate without name personalization. A supervising adult could manually add the participant's name after printing. This approach ensured compliance with youth privacy protections while supporting classroom, family, and group-based participation.

All ES Data Collector certificates were designed to be accessible, including compatibility with screen readers. The certificate workflow reflects Eclipse Soundscapes' commitment to Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles by providing multiple means of representation and expression, flexible access pathways, and privacy-conscious participation options.

All submission forms were designed and tested for accessibility, including the use of screen reader-compatible question formats, clear labeling, logical tab order, and minimal reliance on visual formatting. Question structures were intentionally selected to ensure compatibility across assistive technologies and to reduce cognitive load.

Certificate Issuance and Data Return

Because ES Data Collectors were responsible for mailing microSD cards containing recorded soundscape data back to the project team, one might assume that certificates would be issued only after physical receipt and verification of returned data. While this would have been ideal, logistically, it was not feasible given the anticipated volume of returned devices and limited staffing capacity.

Instead, the Data Collector form included a required prompt asking participants to indicate when they had mailed or planned to mail their microSD card and to provide a calendar date. This design encouraged intentional follow-through while recognizing operational constraints.

Certificates were issued upon completion of the online submission form. This approach reflects a trust-based participatory science model in which volunteer scientists are recognized for their contributions and good-faith participation while data receipt and processing occur through a parallel workflow.

Certificate-related fields, including names and email addresses used for optional personalization, were not included in the publicly released datasets archived on Zenodo.

SciStarter Affiliate Participation and Credit

The Eclipse Soundscapes project partnered with SciStarter to support coordinated participation tracking and volunteer scientist recognition. (Reference: <https://scistarter.org>)

Through the SciStarter Affiliate Program, the ES Data Collector role was listed as an official SciStarter activity and highlighted as an eclipse engagement opportunity. Participation credit could be recorded on a volunteer scientist's SciStarter Dashboard.

To receive SciStarter credit, participants who indicated they were 13 years of age or older were given the option, at the end of the submission form, to enter the email address associated with their SciStarter account. This email address was used solely to transmit participation credit and connect the submission to the participant's SciStarter Dashboard.

Participants under 13 years of age were not provided the option to enter an email address for SciStarter credit, ensuring that contact information from children under 13 was not collected.

Participation credit through SciStarter was optional and did not affect completion of the ES Data Collector role. Email addresses provided for SciStarter credit were not included in the publicly released datasets archived on Zenodo.

Participant-Facing SciStarter Affiliate Information (Verbatim from ES Website, 2023–2024)

Eclipse Soundscapes was a [SciStarter Affiliate](#) project! Participation in any of the roles before April 15, 2024 could be credited to a volunteer's SciStarter Dashboard, connecting ES to a broader community of citizen science projects.

The partnership was mutually beneficial:

SciStarter helped amplify outreach and recruitment, while Eclipse Soundscapes provided volunteers with meaningful opportunities to contribute to NASA-supported science. Together with SunSketchers, we documented this collaboration in a published paper: [A Model for Success: SciStarter Partnerships with Eclipse Soundscapes & SunSketchers](#).

“SciStarter is a globally acclaimed, online citizen science hub where thousands of projects, searchable by location, topic, age level, etc., have been registered by individual project leaders or imported through partnerships with federal governments, NGOs, and universities.” (Learn more about [SciStarter](#))

Audio Data Workflow Overview

The Eclipse Soundscapes audio data workflow was designed to ensure accurate metadata matching, timestamp verification, secure backup, public sharing, and reproducible analysis. Audio data were organized into individual site-level records by ES ID number and geographic location.

Stage 1: Receipt, Sorting, and Metadata Organization

Input:

- Online ES ID registrations (1,310 volunteers) including site location, eclipse time, and eclipse percentage
- 494 returned microSD cards, some including handwritten deployment notes

Process:

- Match each microSD card to its registered ES ID and online location data
- Create and validate a metadata spreadsheet for each site
- If microSD card or online location data is missing, review volunteer-submitted offline notes for manual entry
- Merge metadata with NASA Goddard Space Flight Center eclipse data to confirm eclipse percentage and maximum timing
- Organize datasets into hardcopy backups by ES ID

Note: Manual entry was required when online metadata or timestamps were incomplete.

Stage 2: Raw Data Upload and Backup

Input:

- Validated metadata spreadsheet
- Raw audio files from microSD cards

Process:

- Confirm audio files match the correct ES ID
- Verify timestamps within audio files
- If timestamps are missing, review volunteer notes and manually tag date/time information
- Add verified timing information to metadata
- Upload raw audio and create secure backups
- Zip audio files by site for structured handling

Manual intervention occurred when metadata or timestamps required correction.

Stage 3: Public Data Sharing

Input:

- Data Collection Process information documents
- Verified metadata
- Location-related NASA eclipse data
- Zipped site-level audio files

Process:

- Prepare metadata templates for Zenodo
- Merge site-level data into structured upload formats
- Upload site-level records using ES-developed API tools
- Share raw audio data publicly on Zenodo

All programs and APIs developed for this workflow are openly available in the Eclipse Soundscapes GitHub repository: <https://github.com/ARISA-Lab-LLC/ESCSP>

Stage 4: Soundscape Data Analysis

Stage 4 analysis is documented separately to preserve a clear distinction between data stewardship and scientific analysis.

- Analysis code repository: <https://github.com/BrentPease1/eclipse-traits>
- Companion Zenodo record archiving structured analysis scripts and derived outputs. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15790879>

Scientific Outcomes and Data Use

Audio data collected by ES Data Collectors during the 2023 Annular Solar Eclipse and the 2024 Total Solar Eclipse were analyzed to investigate how avian vocal behavior responds to rapid changes in light conditions.

Research Dataset vs Public Archive

Research datasets required recordings from at least the two days prior to the eclipse and the eclipse day to allow for comparison. However, this requirement did not restrict public archiving. All available high-quality recordings meeting archival standards were shared publicly, regardless of duration, to support broad reuse and future research questions.

Definition of a Verified Site for ES Research purposes

A “verified site” refers to a recording location for which:

- A valid ES ID was registered,
- Accurate latitude and longitude were confirmed,
- Eclipse timing data were successfully linked to the site,
- Audio files contained usable recordings with valid timestamps (or recoverable deployment timing from field notes),
- No major device malfunction or file corruption was detected.
- 5 days of audio recordings

Only sites meeting these criteria were included in formal analysis. However, all high-quality recordings meeting public archive standards were shared on Zenodo, regardless of inclusion in research analyses. See the [Criteria for Inclusion in the Public Archive](#) section for more information.

Across both eclipse events:

- 989 individuals registered AudioMoth devices
 - 2023: 219
 - 2024: 770
- 575 participants completed all submission steps (metadata and audio)
 - 2023: 98
 - 2024: 477
- 353 verified sites were included in formal analysis
 - 2023: 80
 - 2024: 273

These verified sites formed the dataset used for analysis.

Analysis Approach

To process more than 45,000 hours of audio recordings, Eclipse Soundscapes partnered with wildlife biologists specializing in soundscape ecology. The analysis used BirdNET, a machine learning tool developed by the Cornell Lab of Ornithology and Chemnitz University of Technology, to detect and classify bird vocalizations across large datasets. Precise timestamps within the recordings were aligned with NASA eclipse timing data, enabling minute-by-minute analysis of behavioral changes relative to eclipse maximum.

Key Findings (High-Level Summary)

Preliminary results indicate:

- Some daytime bird species reduced vocal activity during totality.
- Crepuscular and nocturnal species showed increased vocalization.
- Vocal activity began decreasing approximately 22 minutes before totality and returned to baseline approximately 49 minutes afterward.

These findings suggest that sensitivity to light conditions plays a significant role in avian behavioral responses to solar eclipses. Full methods and results are documented in related scientific publications and analysis records:

- Pease, B., Gilbert, N., & Severino, M. (2026). *Eclipse Soundscapes Preliminary Findings – How Eclipses Affect Nature as determined by Sound (Recorded Webinar)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18613979>
- Gilbert, N. A., Pease, B. S., Severino, M., & Winter, H. III. (2026). *Photoc niche explains avian behavioral responses to solar eclipses*. *Ecology and Evolution*, 16(2), e73090. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.73090>

Criteria for Inclusion in the Public Archive

To ensure reliability and transparency, recordings included in the public archive met the following criteria:

1. Accurate Time and Date

- The AudioMoth device contained verified timestamps, or
- Date and time were recoverable from volunteer-submitted field notes

2. Device and Data Integrity

- Audio files were complete and not compromised by device malfunction, corrupted microSD cards, or major recording errors.

3. Verified Location

- A valid latitude and longitude were available for the recording site.

Recordings that met these standards were organized into site-level Zenodo records and made publicly available.

This manual reflects training and implementation practices used during the October 14, 2023 Annular Solar Eclipse and the April 8, 2024 Total Solar Eclipse cycles. It is preserved for transparency, reproducibility, and long-term open science documentation.

Appendix 1

2023 Annular Eclipse Free Kit Application Google Form

A red asterisk * indicates a required question

Section 1 of 6

ES:CSP 2023 Annular Eclipse Data Collector Kit Application

YOU MUST BE 13 years or older to participate as a data collector. If you are under 18, a guardian must fill out this form for you.

APPLICATION DEADLINE: 7/10/2023

Please fill out this application if you would like to apply to be an Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project (ES:CSP) Data Collector for the **October 14, 2023 annular eclipse**.

Your contact information will not be sold or shared with any organizations not directly involved in the Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project

Email *

Valid email

This form is collecting emails. [Change settings](#)

I am at 18 years or older. (If you are under 18 this application must be filled out by a guardian.) *

Yes, I am 18 years or older.

No, I am not 18 years or older.

Form continues only if “Yes, I am 18 years old or older” is selected.

Section 2 of 6

Applicant information

Description (optional)

Name: *

Short answer text

Zip code where you would collect data *

Short answer text

Why are you interested in being an ES:CSP Data Collector for the 2023 annular eclipse? *

Long answer text

This application is for ES:CSP 2023 annular eclipse participation. Are you also interested in possibly participating in ES:CSP during the 2024 total solar eclipse? (If you select yes we will email you information when 2024 information becomes available.) *

No, I am only interest in Annular Eclipse October 14, 2023 participation.

Yes, I am also interested in Total Solar Eclipse April 8, 2024 participation

Other:

Please provide your mailing address: (location where the kit would be mailed) *

Long answer text

Section 3 of 6

ES:CSP Volunteer Agreement - Part 1

This agreement sets out the non-contractual arrangements between the Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project and you as an individual volunteering their time to be an EC:CSP Citizen Scientist. The aim of this section is to clearly state what the volunteer can expect from ES:CSP and what ES:CSP expects from the volunteer.

ES:CSP commits to providing:

- Free online asynchronous ES:CSP training which includes: Important eclipse information; Multi-sensory Observation information, and data collection instructions
- Online Accessible Eclipse Learning Resources (Videos/Audio)
- Open lines of communication to answer eclipse and project related questions - via email or the project's FB page
- ES:CSP kit with recording device and materials to accepted applicants interested in data collection activities (if application is accepted)
- Completion Certificates for any participants who take online training quizzes or submit observations/data. (email address required).

ES:CSP Data Collector Training Commitment: Please commit to one of the following. *

- Annular Eclipse 2023 ES:CSP Data Collector Training - I agree to complete ES:CSP Data Collector Trainin...
- I cannot commit to completing ES:CSP Data Collector training at this time.
- Other:

Section 4 of 6

ES:CSP Volunteer Agreement - Part 2

Description (optional)

ES:CSP Data Collection & Submission Commitment: Do you agree to collect audio data for all ^{*} of annular eclipse week by placing the provided AudioMoth device outdoors 2 days before the annular eclipse, retrieving it 2 days after the annular eclipse, and either uploading the data via the eclipse soundscapes website or by mailing the MicroSD card?

- Yes, I agree to collect and share audio data as instructed by the ES:CSP team.
- No, I don't agree to collect and share audio data as instructed by the ES:CSP team.
- Other:

ES:CSP Communication Commitment: Working together to ensure a great experience for everyone is very important to us! Please commit to one or more of the following. ^{*}

- I agree to communicate with the ES:CSP team via email or questionnaires (or other forms of communica...
- I cannot commit to communicating with the ES:CSP team.

Section 5 of 6

ES:CSP Volunteer Agreement - Part 3

Description (optional)

ES:CSP Volunteer Understanding: *

I will be performing volunteer work for the Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project (ES:CSP) without any expectation or contemplation of pay. I am donating my services of my own free will because of my interest in supporting ES:CSP and its mission. I understand that I am not an employee of ES:CSP and I have no expectation of an employment relationship, whether express or implied. I understand that I will not receive any wages, compensation or ES:CSP benefits in exchange for my volunteer service. In addition, I understand that I will not be reimbursed for any personal expenses, such as parking or meals that I incur in performing my volunteer work.

I agree that all inventions, improvements, discoveries, software and writings, whether patentable or copyrightable, that are conceived, made, discovered or written jointly or solely by myself, during the period of volunteer activities or as result of the volunteer activities, shall belong solely and exclusively to NASA, ARISA Lab, and the Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project. I understand that all publications, films, slides, videos, artistic or similar endeavors, resulting from my citizen scientist volunteer services will become the property of NASA, ARISA Lab, and ES:CSP, and as such, will be in the public domain and not subject to copyright laws.

This agreement is the entire agreement of the parties with respect to this matter. No representations have been made or relied on by either party. I release NASA, ARISA Lab, and the Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project and its trustees, officers, employees, agents, and representatives from any and all claims, demands, damages or rights of action for any injuries or property damage or loss I suffer arising out of my participation in the volunteer Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project activities.

PLEASE TYPE NAME TO AGREE:

Short answer text

.....

Section 6 of 6

Questions / Comments

Description (optional)

Please share any questions or comments.

Long answer text

Appendix 2

2024 Total Solar Eclipse Free Kit Application Google Form

A red asterisk * indicates a required question

Section 1 of 6

ES 2024 Total Solar Eclipse Data Collector Kit Application

B I U ↻ 🔍

YOU MUST BE 13 years or older to participate as a data collector. Only people 18 years or older are eligible to apply for a free ES data collector kit. If you are under 18, a guardian/adult must fill out this form for you.

APPLICATION DEADLINE: 1/31/2024

Please fill out this application if you would like to apply to receive a free Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) Data Collector kit for the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse.

Your contact information will not be sold or shared with any organizations not directly involved in the Eclipse Soundscapes Project without your explicit permission.

Email *

Valid email

.....

This form is collecting emails. [Change settings](#)

I am at 18 years or older. (If you are under 18 this application must be filled out by an adult/guardian.) *

Yes, I am 18 years or older.

No, I am not 18 years or older.

How did you hear about this free ES Kit Opportunity?

Short answer text

.....

Form continues only if “Yes, I am 18 years old or older” is selected.

Section 2 of 6

Applicant information

Description (optional)

Name: *

Short answer text

Zip code where you would collect data *

Short answer text

ES Data Collector kits must be mailed to your physical address. Please provide a physical mailing address where you can receive your kit. *(Applications without a physical mailing address will not be considered. No email addresses for this question please.)* *

Long answer text

Section 3 of 6

ES Volunteer Agreement - Part 1

This agreement sets out the non-contractual arrangements between the Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project and you as an individual volunteering their time to be an EC:CSP Citizen Scientist. The aim of this section is to clearly state what the volunteer can expect from ES:CSP and what ES:CSP expects from the volunteer.

ES commits to providing:

- Free online asynchronous ES training which includes: Important eclipse information; location notes information and requirement instructions, and data collection instructions
- Online Accessible Eclipse Learning Resources (Videos/Audio)
- Open lines of communication to answer eclipse and project related questions - via email or the project's FB page
- ES kit with recording device and materials to accepted applicants interested in data collection activities (if application is accepted)
- Completion Certificates for any participants who take online training quizzes or submit observations/data. (email address required).

ES Data Collector Training Commitment: Please commit to one of the following. *

- Total Solar Eclipse 2024 ES Data Collector Training - I agree to review and follow the online ES Data Coll...
- I cannot commit to completing ES Data Collector training at this time.
- Other:

Section 4 of 6

ES Volunteer Agreement - Part 2

Description (optional)

ES Data Collection & Submission Commitment: Do you agree to collect audio data for all of * the total solar eclipse week by placing the provided AudioMoth device outdoors 2 days before the total solar eclipse, retrieving it 2 days after the total solar eclipse, and by mailing the MicroSD card to the ES team?

- Yes, I agree to collect and share audio data as instructed by the ES team.
- No, I don't agree to collect and share audio data as instructed by the ES team.
- Other:

ES:CSP Communication Commitment: Working together to ensure a great experience for * everyone is very important to us! Please commit to one or more of the following.

- I agree to communicate with the ES team via email or questionnaires (or other forms of communication t...
- I cannot commit to communicating with the ES team.

Section 5 of 6

ES Volunteer Agreement - Part 3

Description (optional)

ES Volunteer Understanding:

I will be performing volunteer work for the Eclipse Soundscapes Project (ES) without any expectation or contemplation of pay. I am donating my services of my own free will because of my interest in supporting ES and its mission. I understand that I am not an employee of ES and I have no expectation of an employment relationship, whether express or implied. I understand that I will not receive any wages, compensation or ES benefits in exchange for my volunteer service. In addition, I understand that I will not be reimbursed for any personal expenses, such as parking or meals that I incur in performing my volunteer work.

I agree that all inventions, improvements, discoveries, software and writings, whether patentable or copyrightable, that are conceived, made, discovered or written jointly or solely by myself, during the period of volunteer activities or as result of the volunteer activities, shall belong solely and exclusively to NASA, ARISA Lab, and the Eclipse Soundscapes Project. I understand that all publications, films, slides, videos, artistic or similar endeavors, resulting from my citizen scientist volunteer services will become the property of NASA, ARISA Lab, and ES, and as such, will be in the public domain and not subject to copyright laws.

This agreement is the entire agreement of the parties with respect to this matter. No representations have been made or relied on by either party. I release NASA, ARISA Lab, and the Eclipse Soundscapes Project and its trustees, officers, employees, agents, and representatives from any and all claims, demands, damages or rights of action for any injuries or property damage or loss I suffer arising out of my participation in the volunteer Eclipse Soundscapes Project activities.

PLEASE TYPE NAME TO AGREE:

Short answer text

.....

Section 6 of 6

Questions / Comments

Description (optional)

Please share any questions or comments.

Long answer text

Appendix 3

Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Sign Up - Google form 2024

A red asterisk * indicates a required question

Section 1 of 2

Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Sign Up

B I U

This sign-up is for Data Collector role communication. Signing up does not obligate you to participate. By signing up via this form you agree to receive emails updating you on important steps and deadlines associated with being an ES Data Collector. You may opt out from receiving emails at any time after sign-up by contacting Outreach@ArisaLab.org

This sign-up is also for people who participated as ES Data Collectors in 2023 for the annular eclipse and are interested in participating again for the total solar eclipse in 2024.

ES Data Collection requires equipment. **This sign-up is for Data Collector Role communication. This sign-up is NOT to receive a Free Data Collector kit.** The application process to apply to receive a free Data Collector kit ended (1/31/2024). Alternatively, you can also put together your own Data Collector kit using information from EclipseSoundscapes.org

Este formulario de registro es para la comunicación del rol de recolector de datos. La inscripción no requiere participación. Al registrarse a través de este formulario, acepta recibir correos electrónicos informándole de los pasos y plazos importantes asociados con ser un recolector de datos de ES. Puede optar por no recibir correos electrónicos en cualquier momento después de registrarse comunicándose con Outreach@ArisaLab.org.

Este registro también es para personas que participaron como recolectores de datos de ES en 2023 para el eclipse anular y estén interesados en participar nuevamente para el eclipse solar total de 2024.

La recopilación de datos ES requiere equipo. **Este registro es para la comunicación del rol del recolector de datos. Este registro NO es para recibir un kit de recolección de datos gratuito.** El proceso de solicitud para solicitar recibir un kit de recolección de datos gratuito finalizó (31/01/2024). Alternativamente, también puede crear su propio kit de recopilación de datos utilizando información de EclipseSoundscapes.org.

Email *

Valid email

.....

How did you hear about the Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Role? / ¿Cómo conociste los Eclipse Soundscapes? *

- Google Search
- Texas Master Naturalists
- NASA Website
- SciStarter
- National Federation of the Blind
- friend or family
- library
- school
- Scientific American Article
- "Sounds of Nature" Group
- Other:

What is your State? (Please use standard two-letter abbreviations for US states or territories) ¿Cuál es tu estado? (Utilice abreviaturas estándar de dos letras) *

Short answer text
.....

What is your zip code? ¿Cuál es su código postal? *

Short answer text
.....

Why are you interested in being an Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector for the April 8, 2024 total solar eclipse? ¿Por qué está interesado en ser recopilador de datos de paisajes sonoros de eclipse para el eclipse solar total del 8 de abril de 2024?

Long answer text
.....

Did you participate as an ES Data Collector for the 2023 Annular Eclipse? ¿Participó como recopilador de datos de ES para el eclipse anular de 2023?

Yes / Sí

No

Section 2 of 2

Returning ES Data Collector

You should fill out this section if you already have an ES Data Collector kit from 2023 and will be participating in data collection again in April 2024. Debe completar esta sección si ya tiene un kit de recopilación de datos ES 2023 y participará nuevamente en la recopilación de datos en abril de 2024.

How did you receive your ES Data Collector kit? *

NEBP (National Eclipse Ballooning Project) Team

NASA at My Library Kit

National Federation of the Blind Chapter

ES Facilitator Dr. Lindsay Fuller Team

Texas Master Naturalist Member

Sign-up for a kit via EclipseSoundscapes.org website

Other:

What is your 3-digit Eclipse Soundscapes ID number? *(This number is found on your AudioMoth box and AudioMoth device.)* *

¿Cuál es su número de identificación de 3 dígitos de Eclipse Soundscapes? (Este número se encuentra en su caja AudioMoth y en su dispositivo AudioMoth).

Short answer text
.....

Questions or Comments? *¿Preguntas o comentarios?*

Long answer text
.....

Appendix 4

Re-Using 2023 ES Kit Checklist [English]

Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Checklist

For participants who received a kit from Eclipse Soundscapes in 2023

Before April 5, 2024

- [Sign up](#) to be a Data Collector
- Complete your [Apprentice Training](#)
- [Choose a location](#) to deploy your AudioMoth
- Assemble or review your Data Collector Kit. You will need:
 - 1 [AudioMoth Device](#)
 - 1 waterproof plastic bag
 - 2-3 zip ties
 - 3 AA batteries
 - 1(one) 64GB Extreme UHS Speed Class 3 (U3) microSDXC card
 - 1 padded return envelope
- Review [how to find latitude and longitude](#) in Decimal Degrees (DD) format at your location
- Prepare your AudioMoth. If you received a kit from Eclipse Soundscapes in 2023:
 - Install fresh batteries
 - Install a new SD card
 - [Set the AudioMoth Clock](#)

On April 6, 2024: Bring your Data Collector Kit to your recording location

- Set switch to "Default" to start recording and note your recording start time
- Place AudioMoth in plastic bag and secure to an immovable object (like a tree or pole) using zip ties. The flat green circuit board should face out and the batteries should face in.
- Location notes:
 - Note your latitude and longitude
 - Note any other factors about your environment
- Leave your AudioMoth until April 10

On April 8, 2024: Eclipse Day

- Be an [Eclipse Soundscapes Observer](#) (optional but welcomed)
- Use all of your senses to enjoy the eclipse!

On April 10, 2024: Collect your AudioMoth

- Set switch to "USB/Off" to stop recording and note your stop time

As soon as possible April 10-22, 2024

- Submit your [location notes](#) online
- Remove your SD card from the AudioMoth
- Return your SD card and notes with your location info to ARISA Lab in the padded envelope

*ES Team c/o ARISA Lab
47 High Street Ste 501
Medford MA 02155*

Appendix 5

Using 2024 ES Kit Checklist [English]

Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Checklist

For participants who received a kit from Eclipse Soundscapes in 2024

Before April 5, 2024

- [Sign up](#) to be a Data Collector
- Complete your [Apprentice Training](#)
- [Choose a location](#) to deploy your AudioMoth
- Assemble or review your Data Collector Kit. You will need:
 - 1 [AudioMoth Device](#)
 - 1 waterproof plastic bag
 - 2-3 zip ties
 - 3 AA batteries
 - 1(one) 64GB Extreme UHS Speed Class 3 (U3) microSDXC card
 - 1 padded return envelope
- Review [how to find latitude and longitude](#) in Decimal Degrees (DD) format at your location
- Prepare your AudioMoth. If you received a data collection kit from Eclipse Soundscapes in 2024:
 - Ensure the [clock is set](#)

On April 6, 2024: Bring your Data Collector Kit to your recording location

- Set switch to "Default" to start recording and note your recording start time
- Place AudioMoth in plastic bag and secure to an immovable object (like a tree or pole) using zip ties. The flat green circuit board should face out and the batteries should face in.
- Location notes:
 - Note your latitude and longitude
 - Note any other factors about your environment
- Leave your AudioMoth until April 10

On April 8, 2024: Eclipse Day

- Be an [Eclipse Soundscapes Observer](#) (optional but welcomed)
- Use all of your senses to enjoy the eclipse!

On April 10, 2024: Collect your AudioMoth

- Set switch to "USB/Off" to stop recording and note your stop time

As soon as possible April 10-22, 2024

- Submit your [location notes](#) online
- Remove your SD card from the AudioMoth
- Return your SD card and notes with your location info to ARISA Lab in the padded envelope

*ES Team c/o ARISA Lab
47 High Street Ste 501
Medford MA 02155*

Appendix 6

Using Personal Kit Checklist [English]

Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector Checklist

For participants who are building their own data collection kit

Before April 5, 2024

- [Sign up](#) to be a Data Collector
- Complete your [Apprentice Training](#)
- [Choose a location](#) to deploy your AudioMoth
- Assemble or review your Data Collector Kit. You will need:
 - 1 [AudioMoth Device](#)
 - 1 waterproof plastic bag
 - 2-3 zip ties
 - 3 AA batteries
 - 1(one) 64GB Extreme UHS Speed Class 3 (U3) microSDXC card
 - 1 padded return envelope
- Review [how to find latitude and longitude](#) in Decimal Degrees (DD) format at your location
- Prepare your AudioMoth. If you are building your own data collection kit:
 - [Flash your AudioMoth](#) with Firmware
 - Install your SD card
 - Install your batteries
 - [Set the AudioMoth Clock](#)
 - [Register for a unique ES ID#](#)

On April 6, 2024: Bring your Data Collector Kit to your recording location

- Set switch to "Default" to start recording and note your recording start time
- Place AudioMoth in plastic bag and secure to an immovable object (like a tree or pole) using zip ties. The flat green circuit board should face out and the batteries should face in.
- Location notes:
 - Note your latitude and longitude
 - Note any other factors about your environment
- Leave your AudioMoth until April 10

On April 8, 2024: Eclipse Day

- Be an [Eclipse Soundscapes Observer](#) (optional but welcomed)
- Use all of your senses to enjoy the eclipse!

On April 10, 2024: Collect your AudioMoth

- Set switch to "USB/Off" to stop recording and note your stop time

As soon as possible April 10-22, 2024

- Submit your [location notes](#) online
- Remove your SD card from the AudioMoth
- Return your SD card and notes with your location info to ARISA Lab in the padded envelope

*ES Team c/o ARISA Lab
47 High Street Ste 501
Medford MA 02155*

Appendix 7

Re-Using 2023 ES Kit Checklist [Spanish]

Lista de Verificación de Recopilación de Datos de Eclipse Soundscapes
Para los participantes que recibieron un kit del equipo de ES en 2023

Antes del 5 de Abril de 2024

- [Regístrese](#) para ser un recopilador de datos
- [Complete la capacitación](#) para aprendices
- [Elija una ubicación](#) para utilizar su dispositivo AudioMoth
- Arme o revise su kit de recopilación de datos. Necesitará lo siguiente:
 - Un [dispositivo AudioMoth](#)
 - Una bolsa de plástico a prueba de agua
 - Dos o tres precintos
 - Tres baterías AA
 - Una (1) tarjeta Extreme MicroSDXC, velocidad UHS clase 3 (U3), de 64 GB
 - Un sobre acolchado
- Revise [cómo encontrar la latitud y la longitud](#) en el formato de grados decimales en su ubicación
- Prepare su dispositivo AudioMoth. Si recibió un kit de Eclipse Soundscapes en 2023:
 - Coloque las baterías nuevas
 - Instale la nueva tarjeta SD
 - [Configuración del reloj](#) del dispositivo AudioMoth

pero bien recibido). Utilice todos sus sentidos y disfrute del eclipse.

El 6 de abril de 2024: Traiga su kit de recopilación de datos a la ubicación de grabación (antes del mediodía hora local)

- Mueva el interruptor al modo "Default" para comenzar a grabar y anote la hora de inicio de la grabación
- Coloque el dispositivo AudioMoth en una bolsa de plástico y asegúrelo a un objeto fijo (como un árbol o poste) utilizando los precintos. La placa plana de circuito verde debe mirar hacia fuera y las baterías hacia dentro.
- Notas de la ubicación:
 - Anote la latitud y la longitud
 - Anote cualquier otro aspecto acerca de su entorno
- Deje su dispositivo AudioMoth hasta el 10 de abril

El 10 de abril de 2024: Retire su dispositivo AudioMoth (después de las 5 p.m. hora local)

- Mueva el interruptor al modo "USB/Off" para detener la grabación y anote la hora tan pronto como sea posible.

Del 10 al 22 de abril de 2024:

- Envíe sus [notas de la ubicación](#) en línea
- Retire la tarjeta SD del dispositivo AudioMoth
- Envíe su tarjeta SD y las notas con la información de su ubicación en el sobre acolchado a ARISA Lab.

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Medford MA 02155

El 8 de abril de 2024: Día del eclipse

- [Actúe como observador](#) de Eclipse Soundscapes (este paso es opcional,

Appendix 8

Using 2024 ES Kit Checklist [Spanish]

Lista de Verificación de Recopilación de Datos de Eclipse Soundscapes
Para los participantes que recibieron un kit del equipo de ES en 2024

Antes del 5 de Abril de 2024

- [Regístrese](#) para ser un recopilador de datos
- [Complete la capacitación](#) para aprendices
- [Elija una ubicación](#) para utilizar su dispositivo AudioMoth
- Arme o revise su kit de recopilación de datos. Necesitará lo siguiente:
 - Un [dispositivo AudioMoth](#)
 - Una bolsa de plástico a prueba de agua
 - Dos o tres precintos
 - Tres baterías AA
 - Una (1) tarjeta Extreme MicroSDXC, velocidad UHS clase 3 (U3), de 64 GB
 - Un sobre acolchado
- Revise [cómo encontrar la latitud y la longitud](#) en el formato de grados decimales en su ubicación
- Prepare su dispositivo AudioMoth. Si recibió un kit de Eclipse Soundscapes en 2024:
 - [Configuración del reloj](#) del dispositivo AudioMoth

El 6 de abril de 2024: Traiga su kit de recopilación de datos a la ubicación de grabación (antes del mediodía hora local)

- Mueva el interruptor al modo "Default" para comenzar a grabar y anote la hora de inicio de la grabación
- Coloque el dispositivo AudioMoth en una bolsa de plástico y asegúrelo a un objeto fijo (como un árbol o poste) utilizando los precintos. La placa plana de circuito verde debe mirar hacia fuera y las baterías hacia dentro.
- Notas de la ubicación:
 - Anote la latitud y la longitud
 - Anote cualquier otro aspecto acerca de su entorno
- Deje su dispositivo AudioMoth hasta el 10 de abril

El 10 de abril de 2024: Retire su dispositivo AudioMoth (después de las 5 p.m. hora local)

- Mueva el interruptor al modo "USB/Off" para detener la grabación y anote la hora tan pronto como sea posible.

Del 10 al 22 de abril de 2024:

- Envíe sus [notas de la ubicación](#) en línea
- Retire la tarjeta SD del dispositivo AudioMoth
- Envíe su tarjeta SD y las notas con la información de su ubicación en el sobre acolchado a ARISA Lab.

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El 8 de abril de 2024: Día del eclipse

- [Actúe como observador](#) de Eclipse Soundscapes (este paso es opcional, pero bien recibido).
- Utilice todos sus sentidos y disfrute del eclipse.

Appendix 9

Using Personal Kit Checklist [Spanish]

Lista de Verificación de Recopilación de Datos de Eclipse Soundscapes
Para los participantes que están construyendo su propio kit de recopilación de datos.

Antes del 5 de Abril de 2024

- [Regístrese](#) para ser un recopilador de datos
- [Complete la capacitación](#) para aprendices
- [Elija una ubicación](#) para utilizar su dispositivo AudioMoth
- Arme o revise su kit de recopilación de datos. Necesitará lo siguiente:
 - Un [dispositivo AudioMoth](#)
 - Una bolsa de plástico a prueba de agua
 - Dos o tres precintos
 - Tres baterías AA
 - Una (1) tarjeta Extreme MicroSDXC, velocidad UHS clase 3 (U3), de 64 GB
 - Un sobre acolchado
- Revise [cómo encontrar la latitud y la longitud](#) en el formato de grados decimales en su ubicación
- Prepare su dispositivo AudioMoth. Si está construyendo su propio kit de recopilación de datos:
 - Coloque las baterías
 - Instale la nueva tarjeta SD
 - [Actualice AudioMoth](#) con la versión 1.8.1 de firmware
 - [Configuración del reloj](#) del dispositivo AudioMoth
 - [Registre para obtener un número de identificación](#) de Eclipse Soundscapes

El 6 de abril de 2024: Traiga su kit de recopilación de datos a la ubicación de grabación (antes del mediodía hora local)

- Mueva el interruptor al modo "Default" para comenzar a grabar y anote la hora de inicio de la grabación
- Coloque el dispositivo AudioMoth en una bolsa de plástico y asegúrelo a un objeto fijo (como un árbol o poste) utilizando los precintos. La placa plana de circuito verde debe mirar hacia fuera y las baterías hacia dentro.
- Notas de la ubicación:
 - Anote la latitud y la longitud
 - Anote cualquier otro aspecto acerca de su entorno
- Deje su dispositivo AudioMoth hasta el 10 de abril

El 8 de abril de 2024: Día del eclipse

- [Actúe como observador](#) de Eclipse Soundscapes (este paso es opcional,

pero bien recibido). Utilice todos sus sentidos y disfrute del eclipse.

El 10 de abril de 2024: Retire su dispositivo AudioMoth (después de las 5 p.m. hora local)

- Mueva el interruptor al modo "USB/Off" para detener la grabación y anote la hora tan pronto como sea posible.

Del 10 al 22 de abril de 2024:

- Envíe sus [notas de la ubicación](#) en línea
- Retire la tarjeta SD del dispositivo AudioMoth
- Envíe su tarjeta SD y las notas con la información de su ubicación en el sobre acolchado a ARISA Lab.

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